

EDUCATION TRANSFER KNOWLEDGE 08.

Advanced e-learning system for In-School placement

Project Information

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This is Output 8 of O27 in the EKT Output Series. All public outputs in the series are available from the project website: <https://ektproject.eu>

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1. DESCRIPTION OF THE OUTPUT

This output will require the integration and improvement of different existing tools (provided by our experienced technological partners), contents & functionalities to provide a comprehensive platform to suit the needs of the users, according to the definition from previous WP, as well as to provide access to communication & reporting of online and some offline activities from students to their teachers/ tutors.

This output will be the main milestone of the WP 4

2. THE EKT TECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTION

2.1. Introduction

EKT project developed an advanced e-learning system for in-school teaching practice (in-school placement) by integrating, adapting and improving different existent open source tools (some of them provided by technological partners), as well as designing some new features to provide support for communication, reflection and follow-up for students, teachers and mentors.

Today there are a number of e-learning tools that provide several generic educational services such as communication, documents repository, e-Portfolios, agendas, etc. but there are not specific platforms that support the process of future teachers in-school placement, taking into account a tailored response to the needs of all the participant agents in the process.

The complexity of this task meant the identification of the most appropriate features and tools and their adaptation to create a unified platform, providing a seamless connection and exchange of information between tools to provide an informative dashboard for teachers and students, meeting the methodological requirements and the needs for improvement detected in teaching practices. The challenge was also to make interoperable technological tools provided by both private companies and opensource developments and articulate them around a versatile system of tools and digital resources for training in student teacher's practice.

2.2. Development process

The development of the EKT platform followed the DBR (Design-based Research) methodology. This is an iterative process, where the technical team produced/adapted and tested the integration of several software tools which got validation and feedback from the educational team and final users in successive pilot cycles.

During the process it was essential to synchronize the development and deployment of the different platform versions with the school placement periods in order to be presented to the final users during their internships. After each internship period the different tools were adjusted or new features were proposed, depending on the final user's feedback as well as on the experience and analysis made by the academic partners of the consortium.

As a result, two pilot cycles were developed. The first one (Beta 1) was carried out during the academic year 2021-2022, the second one (Beta 2) was carried out during the academic year 2022-2023. Afterwards, the final version of the platform was published.

Figure 1: EKT platform development phases, based on RBD methodology

2.3. Tools selection

As it was already mentioned, the EKT platform incorporates already existent open-source software tools with own developments. **The selection of the different tools was made considering:**

- The differences between the different educational systems in each of the countries participating in the project, and the results derived from the needs assessment developed in Work package 2 (output 5).
- Each of the main challenges planned, such as horizontal collaboration, interaction, reflection, and personalized follow-up are suited to the defined user roles. These roles have different responsibilities throughout the training process during in-school placement.
- The specific characteristics of the training process, the training sequence and its different stages, as in-school placement implies a gradual and reflective experimentation of the teaching profession. i.e. the Pedagogical and Technological framework for development of professional competences in in-school placement developed in workpackage 3 (output 6).

This required an extensive work to adapt and make all the already existent tools compatible each other (interoperable), but also with the own developments made by the EKT technological partners.

2.4. EKT Platform structure

The EKT platform structure was defined around three principles intended to group the different tools depending on their purpose. Thus, the EKT platform consists in a set of three plus one blocks:

- **Core and management:** Central tools providing login, safety, interoperability, management, and support features.
- **Collaboration services:** Tools providing advanced collaboration using different kinds of documents, communication capabilities (both synchronous and asynchronous) and tasks scheduling features.
- **Training:** Tools supporting students' reflection processes, training tools, learning materials creation and user actions tracking.
- **Maintenance:** In addition, a fourth block emerges to provide shared data storage and backup capabilities.

Each of the previous blocks integrates one or several servers and/or services and have none or several support background servers/services as follows:

Block	Type	Name	Function
Core & management	Server	EKT management	Host core services & applications
Core & management	Service	Nginx	Reverse proxy
Core & management	Service	Apache	Web server
Core & management	Service	EKT CAS	Single Sign On entry point
Core & management	Service	MariaDB	Database management system
Core & management	Service	MongoDB	Database management system for SSO ticketing registry
Core & management	Application	EKT Webservices	Provide cross-system notifications and user sidebar
Core & management	Application	EKT Management	EKT management app
Core & management	Application	EKT Password	EKT Password recovery
Collaboration	Server	EKT Collaboration	Host EKT Nextcloud
Collaboration	Service	Apache	Web server
Collaboration	Service	MariaDB	Database management system
Collaboration	Application	Customized Nextcloud	Frontal application for EKT collaboration
Collaboration	Server	EKT Collabora	Host EKT Collabora
Collaboration	Service	Nginx	Web server
Collaboration	Service	MariaDB	Database management system
Collaboration	Service	RabbitMQ	Messaging protocol
Collaboration	Application	OnlyOffice Community	Cloud based document edition tool
Collaboration	Server	EKT HPB	EKT communications High performance backend
Collaboration	Service	STUN/TURN	Discover NAT devices
Collaboration	Service	NATS	Data message exchange
Collaboration	Service	Janus	WebRTC server
Collaboration	Service	Nextcloud spread signaling	Manage connections between devices
Collaboration	Service	Nginx	Web server
Training	Server	EKT Online campus	Host EKT online campus
Training	Service	MariaDB	Database management system
Training	Service	Apache	Web server
Training	Application	Customized Chamilo	Learning management system with LRS capabilities
Training	Server	EKT creation tool	Host EKT creation tool
Training	Service	MariaDB	Database management system
Training	Service	Apache	Web server
Training	Application	Customized Chamilo Studio	Learning material creation tool
Maintenance	Service	Network File System host	Share data storage across EKT servers
Maintenance	Service	NetBackup	Backup automation solution

Later on, it will be explained in more detail each of the services/servers.

2.5. EKT Platform Architecture

Below we present the diagram of the final infrastructure of the EKT platform. As it was mentioned before, this final product is the result of the two pilot cycles carried out during the EKT project.

Figure 2: EKT platform Architecture

2.6. EKT Platform features evolution

Block	Tool	Pilot 1	Pilot 2	Final version
EKT CORE	Single-sign-on	Partially integrated. Version 6.1.7	Integrated. Version 6.1.7 with security fixes	Integrated. Version 6.6.7
EKT CORE	User management	Integrated. Limited capabilities version 1	Integrated. Complete capabilities version 2	Integrated. Complete capabilities version 3
EKT CORE	University & schools management	Integrated. Limited capabilities Version 1	Integrated. Complete capabilities Version 2	Integrated. Complete capabilities Version 3
EKT CORE	Dashboard	Integrated. Static dashboard Version 1	Integrated. Static dashboard Version 2	Integrated. Dynamic dashboard Version 3
EKT CORE	Core webservices	Unavailable	Unavailable	Integrated
EKT CORE	Learning analytics	Unavailable	Partially integrated. Only data collection. Metabase visualization (for internal use)	Integrated. Data collection & visualization panel integration with Dashboard
EKT CORE	Help section	Integrated	Integrated	Integrated

2. The EKT technological solution

EKT COLLABORATION	Files and documents	Integrated. Nextcloud v23 + EKT customizations v1	Integrated. Nextcloud v24.0.4 + EKT customizations v2	Integrated Nextcloud v24.0.12 + EKT customizations v3
EKT COLLABORATION	Calendar	Integrated. Version 2.3.4	Integrated Version 3.4.2	Integrated Version 3.5.7
EKT COLLABORATION	Chat & videoconference	Integrated. Version 11.3.5	Integrated. Version 14.0.4	Integrated. Version 14.0.10
EKT COLLABORATION	EKT collabora	Integrated. Version gifted_hoover	Integrated. Version gifted_hoover	Integrated. Version gifted_hoover
EKT COLLABORATION	EKT HPB	Integrated. Unstable integration	Integrated. Stable integration	Integrated. Stable integration + fixes
EKT TRAINING	Online Campus	Integrated. Chamilo 1.11.16	Integrated. Chamilo 1.11.16	Integrated. Chamilo 1.11.18
EKT TRAINING	Online Campus Eportfolio	Integrated. Initial release	Integrated. Advanced release	Integrated. Final release
EKT TRAINING	Online Campus Learning Record Store	Integrated. Learning Locker	Integrated. Chamilo 1.11.16	Integrated. Chamilo 1.11.18
EKT TRAINING	Online Campus Extra menu from Webservice	Unavailable	Unavailable	Integrated v0.1
EKT TRAINING	Online Campus Extra Notification connect	Unavailable	Unavailable	Integrated v0.1
EKT TRAINING	Online Campus Experience API	Unavailable	Integrated v0.3	Integrated v0.3
EKT TRAINING	Content Creation	Partially integrated. Content Cloud	Integrated. Chamilo Studio v2022	Integrated. Chamilo Studio v2022
EKT TRAINING	Content Creation Extra menu from Webservice	Unavailable	Unavailable	Integrated v0.1
EKT TRAINING	Content Creation Extra Notification connect	Unavailable	Unavailable	Integrated v0.1
EKT TRAINING	Content creation Experience API	Partially integrated (Content Cloud tool)	Integrated v0.3	Integrated v0.3
EKT MOBILE APP	EKT APP	Not available. Responsive web instead	Not available. Responsive web instead	Available for Android devices

3. EKT PLATFORM COMPONENTS AND FEATURES DESCRIPTION

3.1. EKT CORE

This is the main and most important block of the EKT platform structure. It's purpose is to act as a central core where all the other functions of the system are interconnected. In addition, it hosts the main platform database, where all the relationships between all the EKT elements are stored. The **EKT Core** hosts the **EKT CAS**, the **Management app** and the **Core webservice**.

3.1.1. EKT CAS

The **EKT CAS** (Central Authentication Service) is a single sign-on protocol whose purpose is to permit EKT users to access to all the system applications as if they were one single tool. Given that the EKT platform consists on several applications, by default each of them needs to have a user account. Without the **EKT CAS**, each time a user wanted to access to any of the applications he/she must login with their credentials. Since the applications, by default are isolated from each other, the user data could be inconsistent. This means that in some parts of the application, the user data could be different (passwords, profile information, etc). By using the **EKT CAS** all the user accounts of the different tools of the EKT system share the same user profile and it is only needed to login once, towards the CAS. Thus, the CAS shares all the information with all the parts of the system to let the users navigate fluently as if the EKT platform were only one unique tool. The **EKT CAS** uses as base the Apereo CAS software, but it was adapted to the project needs, setting up the authentication methods and the login/password recovery interfaces.

3.1.2. EKT Management app

This is the **nucleus** and the **most important part** of the EKT system in terms of management. From here all the user accounts, universities, schools, courses, shares, chats and videoconferences are created. In addition, all the relations and associations between user roles, between users and institutions (universities, and schools), and users and courses are created from here.

All the information can be managed from the **dashboard**, an interface adapted to each user role to present the most relevant information and tools at every moment. Apart from all the management, the **learning analytics**¹ visualization and the help section can be accessed from the management app. The EKT Management uses as base system the **Wordpress software** because it is easier to integrate custom developments and plugins. Apart from the Wordpress core, all the EKT management features, visualizations and interfaces are **EKT own developments**.

¹The EKT Learning Analytics is a cross-platform function with two main functions. First of all is to collect information from every user action within the whole EKT platform. All the information are stored into a Learning Record Store hosted by the EKT Online Campus. Then, every user is able to check the learning analytics information (the Depth of the visualized data depends on the user role) related with three blocks: Access to the platform, progress within the ekt courses, and reflection level.

3.1.3. EKT Core Webservices

As it was already said, the EKT platform consists of different tools interconnected. Given that each tool has its own interface, it was decided to unify the appearance of all the applications to ease and simplify the user experience and navigation. Thus, it is needed that every tool include a common **sidebar** to let the users change between the different platform elements easily. As each user role has its own information and relevant tools, it was needed to develop a **dynamic sidebar**. The core webservices task is to generate and to provide those sidebars to all the EKT platform elements as well as to the EKT Mobile App.

In addition, the notification system is included within the sidebar. This means that when the user interacts with different EKT platform elements such as e-portfolio or learning paths, those elements send a notification to the core webservice to let the user know that there are new notifications to check. The EKT Core Webservices is an **EKT own development**.

3.2. EKT Collaboration

This part of the platform is in charge of the **collaborative work** between users. It provides an individual **cloud storage** per user where files can be uploaded. In addition to this, the system allows to create documents, presentations, spreadsheets, etc **collaboratively**. This means that different users can work together on the same document from different computers. Apart from the capacity to store and create documents, the system is capable of creating **“default shared folders”** between EKT users depending on their roles and relationships. As an example, when a student is assigned to a school mentor, a shared folder between them will be created.

Other feature of the EKT collaboration is the **calendar**. It can be used individually but also collaboratively with other users.

Last but not least, we have the **communication tool**. It works both synchronously and asynchronously in form of chat but also as videoconference. EKT users are able to create individual and group chat/videoconference rooms.

EKT Collaboration is based on **Nextcloud software** and **Talk (spreed)** communication plugin. Additional features developed by the EKT team were added, such as analytics collection data, customized interface, cross platform sidebar, user creation “on the fly” and dynamic shared folders.

3.2.1. EKT Collaboration and EKT High performance backend

The previous functionalities can work **limited** in an own server environment. This means that the more users the **least performance**. To avoid this problem, two additional servers were deployed to act as support from the background. First one is **EKT collabora**, based on Onlyoffice document server. It manages all the user interaction with documents and synchronizes the content in real time between users working with the same documents. On the other side, **EKT High Performance Backend** is a server that manages all the videoconference connections between users. It absorbs and distributes all the network traffic generated by users during a videoconference.

Without these two support servers and services, the collaboration experience could be **diminished**, because users do not use to have good and stable internet connections as well as computers and smartphones powerful enough to support high loads of data and traffic. By using them, a **minimal hardware and connection** is needed from each user to have a fluent experience.

3.3. EKT Training

3.3.1. Online Campus

The EKT Online Campus is the key part of the EKT methodology deployment. It is a Learning Management System (LMS) based on Chamilo software but customized by the EKT technical partners to fit with the EKT methodology designed on the previous outputs.

The EKT Online Campus can host as many courses as needed per university. It is highly customizable, this means that any kind of activity such as tasks, quizzes, exercises, links, lessons, etc. can be implemented on each course.

3.3.2. E-portfolio

Apart from the above, the EKT partners have developed a brand-new tool for the LMS whose main function is to generate self-reflection processes during the school placement. This tool is one of the most important milestones of the project, and it is now available worldwide for more than 21 million users.

The EKT e-portfolio **has been transferred to the open source platform Chamilo and is now integrated as an additional functionality available to all users.** This active learning and assessment tool is a milestone since the Chamilo development community, after its evaluation, has considered that it represents an advance and improvement for this e-learning platform, which is one of the best known and used worldwide.

3.3.3. SPOC

Other important part is the EKT SPOC (Small Private Online Course), developed by the academic partners and available for all the EKT users within each of the courses created. The EKT platform integrates the multimedia course developed for the pre-training of EKT system users (output 11) and integrates the data from this training activity into the system analytics.

3.3.4. Learning Record Store

As in the previous parts of the platform, the Online Campus collects data from every user interaction. The data collected by all the parts of the EKT platform is sent and stored within the Learning Record Store, which is hosted by the Online Campus as a database of user actions. Once the user actions are stored, the data is sent to the EKT management under request from the analytics visualization section.

3.3.5. Content Creation tool

A brand-new tool was introduced as a learning materials interactive content generation tool. All users, but specially students are now able to create appealing multimedia materials to be used during the school placement. The tool allows to create contents by including images, audio, video, animations, games, etc. Once finished, the contents can be exported to different standard formats such as scorm, xapi or pdf. It is based on Ludiscape's Chamilo Studio

3.3.6. Connectivity and customizations

Both Online Campus and Content Creation tool have been adapted to the EKT platform appearance and they are connected with the EKT Management since that assignments between users and courses are needed or courses are being requested. Data is exchanged also between the Online Campus/Content Creation and the Core Webservice, as they send notifications from activities done in the e-portfolio, learning paths and contents created. On the other side, the user sidebar is retrieved from the webservice to be displayed on the Online Campus and Content Creation tool.

4. EKT PLATFORM EVOLUTION

As it was shown previously, the platform has evolved during the different piloting phases. Thus, although there were several changes, we provide the most significant ones across the different EKT platform versions.

First pilot:

- Partial integration of CAS Service Providers
- Users' creation manually (management)
- Groups, courses, assignments, and shares management
- Installed Talk plugin for videoconferencing (limited experience)
- Installed EKT collaboration tool (limited api)
- Installed EKT collabora tool
- Partially installed Content creation tool (Netex Content Cloud)
- First e-portfolio implementation
- LRS server installed (Learning locker)

Second pilot:

- Fully CAS Service Providers integration
- Shared folder between group members (management)
- Now tutors can be assigned to groups (management)
- Unused icons/access were hidden
- Bulk user creation through csv file
- Bulk school creation through csv file
- New background, icons, fonts and color for the management section
- Added visual warnings to management
- Added direct accesses to e-portfolio and content creation tool from management tables
- Added possibility to search users by name or surname within the EKT collaboration tools
- Clean-up initial files (collaboration)
- Changed folder colours according to type of share
- Improved videoconference stability with new HPB server and software
- Reactions, emojis and voice messages on chat
- New tags management for e-portfolio
- Possibility to edit own posts (E-portfolio)
- Fixes on export process (e-portfolio)
- New filters (e-portfolio)
- New content creation tool implemented (Chamilo Studio)
- LRS replaced (now we use Internal Chamilo's LRS)
- Learning analytics data collection functions integrated within all the ekt tools.

Final version:

- New dynamic dashboards customized per user role
- New graphic interface for all the platform tools
- New management navigation structure
- New learning analytics visualization section
- Redesigned information pages on management
- Fully responsive design
- New sidebar across all platform tools
- Collapsible sidebar
- New notification center
- EKT Mobile app
- Improved platform stability and performance

Evolution screenshots:

Figure 3: EKT platform Dashboard (version beta-pilot 1)

Figure 4: EKT platform Dashboard (version beta-pilot 1)

Figure 5: EKT platform Dashboard (version beta-pilot 2)

Figure 6: EKT platform Dashboard (Final version post pilot)

Figure 7: EKT platform Main navigation menu (Final version post pilot)

5. ACCESS TO THE EKT TECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTION

The EKT platform is **publicly available** from EKT site <https://ektproject.eu/resources/> and from the following url: <https://app.ektproject.eu>

In order to access and test the EKT platform, you can use some of the following user accounts. Demo accounts are provided to test and visualise the **EKT platform** from the different user profiles described in the **EKT Methodology** (Output 6). The EKT platform adapts to the different user profiles. All of them share a navigation menu that gives access to all the tools and functionalities and incorporates in the central control panel a personalised selection of the most used tools from each role profile.

Also note that the roles of **coordinator and mentor** are carried out from both institutions (school and university) and the decision has been taken that the interface will be the same for each role regardless of the school or academic context. This decision is based on the idea that both professionals (coordinators or mentors) share the same functionalities and data, considering that their collaboration should be **horizontal**, not hierarchical.

Username	Password	Role
ektdemo_admin@cesga.es	ektdemo_2023	Country/university administrator
ektdemo_heicoord@cesga.es	ektdemo_2023	University coordinator
ektdemo_schcoord@cesga.es	ektdemo_2023	School coordinator
ektdemo_heitutor@cesga.es	ektdemo_2023	Academic mentor
ektdemo_schtutor@cesga.es	ektdemo_2023	School mentor
ektdemo_student@cesga.es	ektdemo_2023	Student 1
ektdemo_student2@cesga.es	ektdemo_2023	Student 2
ektdemo_student3@cesga.es	ektdemo_2023	Student 3

Please note that any activity done with those **demo accounts** could be **removed at anytime** by the system administrators for **performance and security reasons**. In addition, the **EKT consortium** will not be responsible of any of the activities and materials created/uploaded by users through the use of those public demo accounts.

6. EKT INSTALLATION GUIDE

This section is addressed to system administrators who want to deploy the EKT platform on their own hardware infrastructure. Here we will provide with virtual machine images to ease the deployment of the different servers.

NOTE: this task is highly complex, and it will require great quantity of hardware resources.

6.1. Minimum system requirements per server

- **EKT Core:** 4 CPU cores, 8GB RAM, 20GB HDD
- **EKT Collaboration:** 4CPU cores, 6GB RAM, 100GB of storage (or more depending on number of users and quota per user)
- **EKT High Performance Backend*:** 8 CPU cores, 16GB RAM, 20GB storage, 512Mbit/s (25 concurrent users sharing webcam)
- **EKT Collabora*:** 2 CPU cores, 4GB RAM, 80GB HDD
- **EKT Online Campus:** 2 CPU cores, 4GB RAM, 20GB HDD
- **EKT Creation Tool:** 2 CPU cores, 4GB RAM, 20GB HDD

Servers marked with an asterisk, are optional, this means that EKT could work without them in **low performance mode**. Note that this will require alternative configurations as the EKT platform images have been compiled to use all the available hardware:

- If **EKT High Performance Backend** is not set-up, all the configurations listed must be empty. Videocalls will work as peer-to-peer connection, being limited to the user's available bandwidth.
- As for **EKT Collabora**, there are two options. It can be installed on the same server as EKT collaboration (will support less concurrent users). Alternatively it can be used other similar plugin (less resource consumption) called "Collabora Online" from the Nextcloud app repository. (Additional CPU/ram/bandwidth could be required for EKT Collaboration)

Access to the images:

Image	Address	Login/password
EKT CORE	https://ektproject.eu/resources	root ektuser2023
EKT HPB	https://ektproject.eu/resources	root ektuser2023
EKT Collaboration	https://ektproject.eu/resources	root ektuser2023
EKT Online Campus	https://ektproject.eu/resources	root ektuser2023
EKT Content Creation	https://ektproject.eu/resources	root ektuser2023

6.2. EKT CORE Installation guidelines

6.2.1. Prepare access URL's

All the image is configured to use the **following URL's**:

- app.ektproject.eu
- cas.ektproject.eu
- ektws.cesga.es
- nc.ektproject.eu
- chamilo.ektproject.eu
- cs.ektproject.eu

At this point we have **two options**:

- Edit our local hosts file pointing the real IP address towards the domains (only for demo purposes, not for production environments) Do the same on image' /etc/hosts file
- Edit the domains with our own ones (production environments). Comment the image' / etc/hosts file

If we choose the **second option**, we need to open the source code and search&replace the domains with the desired ones.

The locations to scan, search&replace are the following:

- Nginx
 - /etc/nginx/sites-available/cas.ektproject.eu.conf
 - /etc/nginx/sites-available/apache.conf
 - /etc/nginx/sites-available/ektws.conf
- Apache
 - /etc/apache2/sites-enabled/000-app.ektproject.eu-ssl.conf
 - /etc/apache2/sites-enabled/000-app.ektproject.eu.conf
 - /etc/apache2/sites-enabled/000-cas-ektproject.eu-ssl.conf
 - /etc/apache2/sites-enabled/000-ektwscesga.es-ssl.conf
- EKT CAS
 - /etc/cas/config/cas.properties
 - /etc/cas/saml/EKTApp.xml
 - /etc/cas/saml/EKTNextcloudSP.xml
 - /etc/cas/saml/idp-metadata.xml
 - /etc/cas/services/EKTApp-10000001.json
 - /etc/cas/services/EKTChamilo-10000003.json
 - /etc/cas/services/EKTChamiloStudio-10000004.json
 - /etc/cas/services/EKTNextCloud-10000002

- EKT Webservice (scan the entire folder&subfolders)
 - /var/www/html/ektws
- EKT management app (scan the entire folder&subfolders)
 - /var/www/html/app.ektproject.eu
- EKT Core webservices (scan the entire folder&subfolders)
 - /var/www/html/ektws

6.2.2. Generate SSL certificates

Although we provide the certificates, they can be expired when you try to deploy the image. The certbot utility is preinstalled.

You'll need to issue certificates for the **following services**:

- EKT CAS (by default cas.ektproject.eu)
- EKT management app (by default app.ektproject.eu)
- EKT webservices (by default ektws.cesga.es)

Certificates are deployed under the /etc/letsencrypt/live folder

If you issue **your own certificates** you'll have to:

- Edit the virtualhosts in nginx/apache2 if needed to match the new one paths.
- Reload apache2/nginx configurations

6.2.3. Ports

By default, the system firewall (ufw) is disabled. For security reasons we strongly recommend you to open 80 and 443 ports only.

6.2.4. PHP configuration

It is needed to configure php-fpm according with the server hardware. The following file should be edited if you decide to use a different hardware configuration than the specified previously.

/etc/php/7.4/fpm/pool.d/www.conf

It is needed to adapt the following values. You can use the following calculator to select the values: <https://spot13.com/pmcalculator/>

- pm.max_children = 28
- pm.start_servers = 7
- pm.min_spare_servers = 7
- pm.max_spare_servers = 21

After doing that it is needed to restart the php service with the following command: `systemctl restart php7.4-fpm.service`

EKT Learning record store:

- **Username:** LRSEKT
- **Password:** LRSEKT2023

EKT Collaboration:

- **Username:** superadmin
- **Password:** ekt_user2023

All those credentials are stored in the following files:

- /var/www/app.ektproject.eu/wp-content/themes/ekt-theme/functions/template-functions.php
- /var/www/app.ektproject.eu/wp-content/themes/ekt-theme/functions/chamilo-functions.php
- /var/www/app.ektproject.eu/wp-content/themes/ekt-theme/functions/csfunctions.php
- /var/www/app.ektproject.eu/wp-content/themes/ekt-theme/functions/nc-functions.php

6.2.8. EKT management

In order to allow the EKT management to connect with the other platform servers, we need to edit the following file:

- /var/www/app.ektproject.eu/wp-content/themes/ekt-theme/functions/db-connection.php
 - Replace the actual IP with the final IP of the EKT Online Campus server: `$chamilo_db_host = '193.144.42.85';`

Once you have all the vm's installed you can start using the EKT management tool. By default, there are some demo accounts created to start with.

Username	Password	Role
default@ektproject.eu	ekt_user2023	Superadmin (can create universities)
admin@ektproject.eu	ekt_user2023	University administrator
student@ektproject.eu	ekt_user2023	Student
academiccoordinator@ektproject.eu	ekt_user2023	Academic coordinator
academicmentor@ektproject.eu	ekt_user2023	Academic mentor
schoolcoordinator@ektproject.eu	ekt_user2023	School coordinator
schoolmentor@ektproject.eu	ekt_user2023	School mentor

PLEASE NOTE: the Superadmin account must be used only to create universities and the first admin user related with each university. Those operations can be done from the following urls:

- <https://app.ektproject.eu/create-university>
- <https://app.ektproject.eu/create-users>

IMPORTANT TO NOTE: if you decide to change the `app.ektproject.eu` url with your desired one, one extra step is needed in order to configure the EKT management tool.

You need to login with the superadmin account, go to `https://app.ektproject.eu/wp-admin/options-general.php` and replace the urls with the new one.

Also if you have edited/issued your custom domains, you need to add edit the URL's and certificates here: https://app.ektproject.eu/wp-admin/options-general.php?page=onelogin_saml_configuration

- Service provider X.509 certificate: Add your custom generated certificate public key
- Service provider private key: Add your custom generated private key
- X.509 Certificate: The one that you'll find on EKT CORE server on `/etc/cas/saml/idp-signing.crt` file
- Once everything is done, you will be able to download the XML metadata file to paste into `/etc/cas/saml/EKTAApp.xml` file

6.2.9. Services

These are the commands to manage the VM services:

- `Systemctl start|stop|status cas`
- `Systemctl start|stop|restart|status mariadb`
- `Systemctl start|stop|restart|status mongod`
- `Systemctl start|stop|restart|status|reload nginx`
- `Systemctl start|stop|restart|status|reload apache2`
- `Systemctl start|stop|restart|status php7.4-fpm.service`

6.2.10. Service' user&passwords

Service	User	Password
MariaDB	root	ekt_user2023
MariaDB	ekt_user	ekt_user2023
MongoDB	ekt_cas	ekt_cas2023

6.3. EKT High performance backend installation guidelines

The EKT high performance backend is ready to be used, just a few configurations are needed:

6.3.1. Access URL's

By default it is used the `signalingprod.ektproject.eu` URL to access to the HPB capabilities. If you need to use your own domain, you will need to replace the URL accordingly within the following files:

- `/etc/nginx/sites-enabled/signaling`
- `/etc/turnserver.conf`
- `/etc/signaling/server.conf`

6.3.2. Allow frontend connections

If you use your custom EKT collaboration URL, you need to allow it to connect to the HPB. To do so, edit the `/etc/signaling/server.conf` file and replace the URL under the `[ekt_nextcloud_1]` block.

6.3.3. API Key's

You can use the built-in api keys but for security reasons it is desirable to create a new set of keys. We will need to generate:

- **Turn secret key:** `openssl rand -hex 32`
- **Turn api key:** `openssl rand -base64 16`
- **Nextcloud secret key:** `openssl rand -hex 16`
- **Session block-key:** `openssl rand -hex 16`
- **Session hash-key:** `openssl rand -hex 16`

Now that we have the 5 keys ready we need to add them to their respective blocks

- File: `/etc/signaling/server.conf`
 - `[sessions]` hashkey and blockkey
 - `[ekt_nextcloud_1]` secret
 - `[turn]` apikey and secret

After modifying all the keys, all the services need to be restarted.

6.3.4. Generate SSL certificates

Although we provide the certificates, they can be expired when you try to deploy the image. The certbot utility is preinstalled.

You'll need to issue certificates for the following services:

- EKT HPB (by default `signalingprod.ektproject.eu`)

Certificates are deployed under the `/etc/letsencrypt/live` folder

If you issue your own certificates you'll have to:

- Edit the `/etc/nginx/sites-available/signaling` file if needed to match the new one paths.
- Reload nginx configuration

6.3.5. Ports

By default, the system firewall (ufw) is disabled. For security reasons we strongly recommend you to open 80, 443 and 3478 ports only.

6.3.6. Services

These are the commands to manage the VM services:

- `systemctl start|stop|restart|status|reload nginx`
- `systemctl start|stop|restart|status janus`
- `systemctl start|stop|restart|status signaling`
- `systemctl start|stop|restart|status coturn`
- `docker start|stop NATSSERVER`
- `docker ps` (check container health)

6.4. EKT Collabora installation guidelines

We do not provide a VM image for this server as it does not require any custom adjustment. It is based on OnlyOffice DocumentServer, so we address you to the official installation guide to setup your own server.

<https://github.com/ONLYOFFICE/DocumentServer>

6.5. EKT Collaboration installation guidelines

The EKT collaboration is ready to be used, just a few configurations are needed:

6.5.1. Access URL's

By default it is used the `nc.ektproject.eu` URL to access to the EKT Collaboration capabilities. If you need to use your own domain, you will need to replace the URL accordingly within the following files:

- `/etc/apache2/sites-enabled/nc.ektproject.eu-redirect.conf`
- `/etc/apache2/sites-enabled/nc.ektproject.eu-ssl.conf`

6.5.2. Generate SSL certificates

Although we provide the certificates, they can be expired when you try to deploy the image. The certbot utility is preinstalled.

You'll need to issue certificates for the following services:

- EKT Collaboration (by default `nc.ektproject.eu`)

Certificates are deployed under the `/etc/letsencrypt/live` folder

If you issue your own certificates you'll have to:

- Edit the `/etc/apache2/sites-enabled/nc.ektproject.eu-ssl.conf` file if needed to match the new one paths.
- Reload apache2 configuration

6.5.3. PHP configuration

It is needed to configure php-fpm according with the server hardware. The following file should be edited if you decide to use a different hardware configuration than the specified previously.

/etc/php/8.1/fpm/pool.d/www.conf

It is needed to adapt the following values. You can use the following calculator to select the values: <https://spot13.com/pmcalculator/>

- pm.max_children = 28
- pm.start_servers = 7
- pm.min_spare_servers = 7
- pm.max_spare_servers = 21

After doing that it is needed to restart the php service with the following command: `systemctl restart php8.1-fpm.service`

6.5.4. Access to the configuration settings

First of all, if you have customized your Collaboration or your Core Webservices URL you'll have to set it up on the following file: `/var/www/nextcloud/config/config.php`

Next step is to configure the SSO and HPB. To do so, you need to login with the local superadmin account. Please note that if you changed the domain, you'll have to use the login URL according to the new domain.

Username	Password	URL
Superadmin	ekt_2023	https://nc.ektproject.eu/login?direct=1

6.5.5. Configure EKT High Performance Backend

Once we are logged, we need to go to <https://nc.ektproject.eu/settings/admin/talk> to setup the HPB. (This is not mandatory, if we do not establish an HPB, the videoconference capabilities will work as a peer-to-peer connections).

- **Stun server:** `signalingprod.ektproject.eu:3478` (use your own domain if needed)
- **Turn servers:**
 - Only turn
 - URL: `Signalingprod.ektproject.eu:3478` (use your own domain if needed)
 - Secret: Turn secret key generated while configuring EKT HPB
 - UDP and TCP
- **High performance backend**
 - URL: <https://signalingprod.ektproject.eu/standalone-signaling>
 - Secret: Nextcloud secret key generated while configuring EKT HPB

6.5.6. Configure SSO

In order to allow the the EKT Collaboration to login through the CAS, we need to edit the following configurations: <https://nc.ektproject.eu/settings/admin/saml>

Please note that those configurations have to be changed only if you have edited/issued your own domain certificates.

Service Provider settings:

- **Service provider X.509 certificate:** Add your custom generated certificate public key
- **Service provider private key:** Add your custom generated private key

IdP configurations:

- **IdP identifier:** <https://cas.ektproject.eu/idp>
- **Target IdP URL:** <https://cas.ektproject.eu/cas/idp/profile/SAML2/POST-SimpleSign/SSO>

Optional IdP configurations:

- **IdP SLO address:** <https://cas.ektproject.eu/cas/idp/profile/SAML2/Redirect/SLO>
- **IdP public certificate:** The one that you'll find on EKT CORE server on /etc/cas/saml/idp-signing.crt file

Once everything is done, you will be able to download the XML metadata file to paste into the EKT CORE server on /etc/cas/saml/EKTNextcloud.xml

6.5.7. Services

These are the commands to manage the VM services:

- Systemctl start|stop|restart|status mariadb
- Systemctl start|stop|restart|status|reload apache2
- Systemctl start|stop|restart|status php8.1-fpm.service

6.5.8. Service' user&passwords

Service	User	Password
MariaDB	root	ekt_user2023
MariaDB	ekt_user	ekt_user2023

6.5.9. Ports

By default, the system firewall (ufw) is disabled. For security reasons we strongly recommend you to open 80 and 443 ports only.

6.6. EKT Online Campus installation guidelines

6.6.1. Access URL's

By default, it is used the `chamilo.ektproject.eu` URL to access to the EKT Online Campus. If you need to use your own domain, you will need to replace the URL accordingly within the following file:

- `/etc/apache2/sites-enabled/chamilo.ektproject.eu.conf`

6.6.2. Generate SSL certificates

Although we provide the certificates, they can be expired when you try to deploy the image. The certbot utility is preinstalled.

You'll need to issue certificates for the following services:

- EKT Online Campus (by default `chamilo.ektproject.eu`)

Certificates are deployed under the `/etc/letsencrypt/live` folder

If you issue your own certificates you'll have to:

- Edit the virtualhosts in apache2 if needed to match the new one paths.
- Reload apache2 configurations

6.6.3. Configure Chamilo

Now it is time to configure the online campus. If you have changed the online campus or the EKT Management URL's you'll need to edit the following strings (`app.ektproject.eu` and `chamilo.ektproject.eu`) on the these files:

- `/var/www/chamilo.abrahamfelpeto.es/www/app/config/configuration.php`
- `/var/www/chamilo.abrahamfelpeto.es/www/app/config/auth.conf.php`

Also, you'll need to update the following configurations into the database:

- `update settings_current set selected_value "CASURL" where variable = "cas_server";`
- `update settings_current set selected_value "WSNURL" where variable = "externalnotificationconnect_notification_url";`
- `update settings_current set selected_value "WSAURL" where variable = "externalnotificationconnect_auth_url";`
- `update settings_current set selected_value "WSMMU" where variable = "extramenufromwebservice_mobile_menu_url";`
- `update settings_current set selected_value "WSNMU" where variable = "extramenufromwebservice_normal_menu_url";`
- `update settings_current set selected_value "WSAU" where variable = "extramenufromwebservice_authentication_url";`
- `update settings_current set selected_value "LRSURL" where variable = "xapi_lrs_url";`

Being the values by default:

- CASURL: cas.ektproject.eu/cas
- WSNURL: <https://ektws.cesga.es/api/v1/notification>
- WSAURL: <https://ektws.cesga.es/api/v1/user-auth>
- WSMMU: <https://ektws.cesga.es/api/v1/user-sidebar-mobile>
- WSNMU: <https://ektws.cesga.es/api/v1/user-sidebar>
- WSAU: <https://ektws.cesga.es/api/v1/user-auth>
- LRSURL: <https://chamilo.ektproject.eu/plugin/xapi/lrs.php>

6.6.4. Services

These are the commands to manage the VM services:

- Systemctl start|stop|restart|status mariadb
- Systemctl start|stop|restart|status|reload apache2

6.6.5. Service' user&passwords

Service	User	Password
MariaDB	root	ekt_user2023
MariaDB	ekt_user	ekt_user2023
Local webservice	webservices@ektproject.eu	ekt_user2023
Internal LRS	EKTLRS	LRSEKT2023

6.6.6. Ports

By default, the system firewall (ufw) is disabled. For security reasons we strongly recommend you to open 80 and 443 ports only.

6.7. EKT Content Creation installation guidelines

6.7.1. Access URL´s

By default, it is used the cs.ektproject.eu URL to access to the EKT Online Campus. If you need to use your own domain, you will need to replace the URL accordingly within the following file:

- /etc/apache2/sites-enabled/cs.ektproject.eu.conf

6.7.2. Generate SSL certificates

Although we provide the certificates, they can be expired when you try to deploy the image. The certbot utility is preinstalled.

You'll need to issue certificates for the following services:

- EKT Content Creation (by default cs.ektproject.eu)

Certificates are deployed under the /etc/letsencrypt/live folder

If you issue your own certificates you'll have to:

- Edit the virtualhosts in apache2 if needed to match the new one paths.
- Reload apache2 configurations

6.7.3. Configure Chamilo

Now it is time to configure the online campus. If you have changed the online campus or the EKT Management URL's you'll need to edit the following strings (app.ektproject.eu and chamilo.ektproject.eu) on the these files:

- /var/www/cs.abrahamfelpeto.es/www/app/config/configuration.php
- /var/www/cs.abrahamfelpeto.es/www/app/config/auth.conf.php

Also, you'll need to update the following configurations into the database:

- update settings_current set selected_value "CASURL" where variable = "cas_server";
- update settings_current set selected_value "WSNURL" where variable = "externalnotificationconnect_notification_url";
- update settings_current set selected_value "WSAURL" where variable = "externalnotificationconnect_auth_url";
- update settings_current set selected_value "WSMMU" where variable = "extramenufromwebservice_mobile_menu_url";
- update settings_current set selected_value "WSNMU" where variable = "extramenufromwebservice_normal_menu_url";
- update settings_current set selected_value "WSAU" where variable = "extramenufromwebservice_authentication_url";
- update settings_current set selected_value "LRSURL" where variable = "xapi_lrs_url";

Being the values by default:

- CASURL: cas.ektproject.eu/cas
- WSNURL: <https://ektws.cesga.es/api/v1/notification>
- WSAURL: <https://ektws.cesga.es/api/v1/user-auth>
- WSMMU: <https://ektws.cesga.es/api/v1/user-sidebar-mobile>
- WSNMU: <https://ektws.cesga.es/api/v1/user-sidebar>
- WSAU: <https://ektws.cesga.es/api/v1/user-auth>
- LRSURL: <https://chamilo.ektproject.eu/plugin/xapi/lrs.php>

6.7.4. Services

These are the commands to manage the VM services:

- Systemctl start|stop|restart|status mariadb
- Systemctl start|stop|restart|status|reload apache2

6.7.5. Service' user&passwords

Service	User	Password
MariaDB	root	ekt_user2023
MariaDB	ekt_user	ekt_user2023
Local webservice	webservices@ektproject.eu	ekt_user2023

6.7.6. Ports

By default, the system firewall (ufw) is disabled. For security reasons we strongly recommend you to open 80 and 443 ports only.

Project Partners

Universidade do Minho

Editor:

Santiago de Compostela: Grupo de investigación de
Tecnología Educativa (USC).
<https://www.tecnoeduc.es/>

1. Mentors and student teachers materials

> **O6-WP3 Educational and technological framework**

> **O8-WP4 Advanced e-learning system**

(Select the preferred language in the browser. To test EKT advanced e-learning system, use the credentials available in O8-WP4 report)

- English
- Spanish
- Deutsch
- Portuguese

> **O9-WP4 Mobile app development**

[Download Android version](#)

(To test EKT advanced e-learning system, use the credentials

available in O9-WP4 report)

> **O10-WP5 Training platform for SPOC**

> **O11-WP5 Training contents PHW**

Visualization links

- English
- Spanish
- German
- Portuguese

Scorm download

- English
- Spanish
- German
- Portuguese

> **O13-WP6 Pilot guide**

- English
- German
- Portuguese
- Spanish

2. Reports

> **O5-WP2 Report on in-school placements needs and possibilities of the technologies**

> **O7-WP4 Technical analysis report**

> **O14-WP6 Pilot report**

> **O17-WP7 Evaluation of users satisfaction**

> **O18-WP7 Evaluation on impact of EKT proposal**

3. Dissemination materials

3.1 Scientific publications, Conference papers & Theses

> **(O23-WP8) Press release scientific articles**

- Fernández-Morante, C., Cebreiro-López, B., Rodríguez-Malmierca, M.-J., & Casal-Otero, L. (2021). Adaptive Learning Supported by Learning Analytics for Student Teachers' Personalized Training during in-School Practices. *Sustainability*, 14(1), 124. MDPI AG. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su14010124>
- Brandão Carvalho, J.A. & Fernández-Morante, C., et al. (2023). Report on in-school placements needs and possibilities of the technologies (EKT Output 5). Universidade do Minho. Instituto de

Educação. Centro de Investigação em Educação. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7806236>

- Fernández-Morante, M.C., Bienzle, H., & et al. (2023). *Smart Technologies for Innovation in Teacher Training. The EKT Handbook*. Zenodo. Die Berater Unternehmensberatungs GmbH. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7818021>
- Leránoz-Iglesias, M. M., Fernández-Morante, C., Cebreiro-López, B., & Abeal-Pereira, C. (2023). Study on the Collaboration between University and Educational Centers Mentors in the Development of the In-School Education Placements in Official University Degrees Qualifying for the Teaching Profession: The Case of the University of Santiago de Compostela. *Education Sciences*, 13(2), 104. MDPI AG. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/educsci13020104>
- Casal-Otero, L., Catala, A., Fernández-Morante, C. et al. AI literacy in K-12: a systematic literature review. *IJ STEM Ed* 10, 29 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-023-00418-7>

> (O24-WP8) Presentations in conferences and events at european and wider level

- Egan, A., Revyakina, E., Georgeson, J., Cebreiro López, B., Fernández Morante, C., Latorre Ruiz, E. & Strasser, T. (2021). EKT, a trans-national platform to support school placement. In E. Langran & L. Archambault (Eds.), *Proceedings of Society for Information Technology & Teacher Education International Conference* (pp. 656-661). Online, United States: Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE). Retrieved April 3, 2023 from <https://www.learntechlib.org/primary/p/219196/>.

- Fernández-Morante, C., Cebreiro, B., Casal-Otero, L., Leránoz-Iglesias, M., Rodríguez-Malmierca, M. J., & Felpeto-Guerrero, A. (noviembre,2022). EKT Una plataforma integral para el soporte de futuros/as docentes. (p.378–380) [Comunicación]. XXV Congreso Internacional EDUTEC 2022, Palma, España.
<https://edutec2022.uib.es/libro-de-actas/>
- Fernández-Morante, C., Cebreiro, B., Latorre Ruiz, E., e Casal, L., (2022). Las tecnologías emergentes como herramienta de apoyo en el Prácticum de la formación inicial del profesorado. International congress education and knowledge. ICON ISBN: 978-84-19312-37-2
- Egan, A., Georgeson, J., Revyakina, E., Strasser, T., Cebreiro, B., Fernandez-Morante, C. e Latorre-Ruiz, E. (2022). EKT, a pilot project exploring the use and impact of a smart technological system to support school placement in five European countries. In E. Langran (Ed.), *Proceedings of Society for Information Technology & Teacher Education International Conference* (pp. 2167-2172). San Diego, CA, United States: Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE). Retrieved May 3, 2022 from <https://www.learntechlib.org/primary/p/221048/>
- Egan, A., Georgeson, J., Revyakina, E., Fernandez Morante, C., Latorre Ruiz, E., & Strasser, T. (2023). EKT, a project exploring the use and impact of a smart technological system to support school placement in five European countries, a final report. In E.Langran (Ed.), *Proceedings of Society for Information Technology & Teacher Education International Conference* (pp. 1542 – 1549). New Orleans, LA, United States: Association for the Advancement

of Computing in Education (ACE). Retrieved 3 April, 2023 from <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/222030>.

- Fernández-Morante, C., Casal-Otero, L., Cebreiro, B., Mareque León, F., Rodríguez Malmierca, M.J. & Felpeto Guerrero, A. (2023). EKT methodology: an open and collaborative strategy to facilitate school placements for future teachers. In . Elizabeth Langran (Ed.), *Proceedings of Society for Information Technology & Teacher Education International Conference* (pp. 1534-1536). New Orleans, LA, United States: Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (ACE). Retrieved April 3, 2023 from <https://www.learntechlib.org/primary/p/222028/>.
- Felpeto-Guerrero, A., Rodríguez-Malmierca, M.J., Fernández-Morante, C. & Cebreiro-López, B. (2023). Pilot evaluation of the EKT trans-national elearning platform to support in school placement. In Elizabeth Langran (Ed.), *Proceedings of Society for Information Technology & Teacher Education International Conference* (pp. 973-978). New Orleans, LA, United States: Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (ACE). Retrieved April 3, 2023 from <https://www.learntechlib.org/primary/p/221954/>.

3.2 Doctoral theses

Two PhD thesis have been developed within the framework of the EKT project. One related to the study of needs and the other to the development of the EKT system

- **Title:** In-School Placements in Initial Teacher Education: needs study

for the design of an innovative, collaborative methodology supported by intelligent technologies (Smart Tech).

Author: Martin Leranoz Iglesias

Directors: M. Carmen Fernández Morante (USC) and Beatriz Cebreiro López (USC).

PhD program in Education

University: University of Santiago de Compostela

Status: Finished in process of thesis defense

- **Title:** Design of a virtual collaborative and learning environment for In-School Placements: the EKT Smart system.

Author: Abraham Felpeto Martínez

Directors: M.Carmen Fernández Morante (USC) and Maria José Rodríguez Malmierca (CESGA)

PhD Inter-University Program in Equity and Innovation in Education

University: University of Santiago de Compostela, University of Oviedo, University of Cantabria, University of A Coruña and University of Vigo

Status: In progress

3.3 Handbook for in school placements (O25-WP8)

- [Smart technologies for innovation in teacher training. the ekt handbook \(English\)](#)
- [Tecnologías inteligentes para innovación en la formación del profesorado. el manual ekt \(Español\)](#)
- [Tecnologias inteligentes para inovação na formação de professores. o manual do ekt \(Português\)](#)
- [Technologies intelligentes pour l'innovation dans la formation des enseignants. le manuel ekt \(Français\)](#)
- [Untelligente Technologien für innovation in der lehrerausbildung. das](#)

ekt-handbuch (Deutsch)

3.4 Multimedia material

- Promotional videos. (Coming soon)
- Youtube Canal

3.5 Newsletters

> O28-WP8 EKT newsletters

- Newsletter 1
- Newsletter 2
- Newsletter 3

3.6 Brochure

> O21-WP8 Project poster

Project posters:

- Poster 1
- Poster 2

Brochure:

- English
- Español

- Deutsch
- Português
- Français

3.7 EACEA Erasmus+ Knowledge Alliances Dissemination Sheet

EACEA Erasmus+ Knowledge Alliances Dissemination Sheet

3.8 Media news

(Coming soon)

3.9 Final conference

> O4-WP1 Final International Conference

The final conference of the **EKT Project** **Smart Technologies for Innovation in Teacher Training** was held on 13 April 2023 in the auditorium of the Faculty of Education of the University of Santiago de Compostela and streamed online.

The conference generated a lot of attention. 352 students, teachers, school principals, researchers, teacher trainers, educators and managers of ITE institutions and e-learning practitioners from 52 nationalities registered for event. In the end 112 persons participated in person, while 235 people attended online.

EDUCATIONAL KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

Co-funded by the Erasmus+ Programme of the European Union

EKT Project Final Conference
Smart Technologies for Innovation
in Teacher Training

13, APRIL 23 | 11 A.M. CET

Faculty of Education Sciences, Campus Vida
 University of Santiago de Compostela

Coordinator: USC (UNIVERSIDADE DE SANTIAGO DE COMPOSTELA) www.ektproject.eu

Partners: CESCA, die Berater, MARNO, FH Wien, lusoinfo multimedia, editora, BeezNest

Streaming: Registration: <https://ektproject.eu/conference/>

3.10 National events

> O26-WP8 EKT national events

SPANISH NATIONAL EVENT 1:

La Coruña- Spain (30 January-16h). Presentation and launch of the results of the EKT project at the Faculty of Education in La Coruña (University of Coruña-UDC) to Educación Máster coordinators, internship coordinators and master's degree students. In Education Faculty of la Coruña the presentation will take place in a specific event of the EKT project.

SPANISH NATIONAL EVENT 2:

Almeria, Andalusia, 23-24 March. Presentation and launching of the results of the EKT project to the Deans of Education of all the Andalusian Faculties and to their Internship teams and managers. The presentation will take place as part of the programme of the annual Assembly of the Andalusian Conference of Deans of Education.

SPANISH NATIONAL EVENT 3:

Alicante, 27 March Presentation and launching of the results of the EKT project in the Faculty of Education of Alicante to vice-chancellors for technology at universities, e-learning researchers, internship coordinators, tutors and students of secondary education. In Alicante, the presentation will take place within the framework of the Education Faculty Cultural week with a specific EKT workshop.

SPANISH NATIONAL EVENT 4:

San Sebastian, Basque Country, 27-28 April 2023. Presentation and launch of the results of the EKT project to the Deans of Education of all the Faculties of Education in Spain and to their teams and those responsible for Internships. The presentation will take place as part of the programme of the Annual monographic meeting of the National Conference of Deans of Education

(<http://www.conferenciadecanososeducacion.es/>)

3.11 O27-WP8 Report on exploitation and dissemination plan

(Coming soon)

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

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1. Mentors and student teachers materials

> O6-WP3 Educational and technological framework

> O8-WP4 Advanced e-learning system

(Select the preferred language in the browser. To test EKT advanced e-learning system, use the credentials available in O8-WP4 report)

- English
- Spanish
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> O9-WP4 Mobile app development

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Visualization links

- English
- Spanish
- German
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Scorm download

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> **O13-WP6 Pilot guide**

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3. Dissemination materials

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PhD program in Education

University: University of Santiago de Compostela

Status: Finished in process of thesis defense

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Directors: M.Carmen Fernández Morante (USC) and Maria José Rodríguez Malmierca (CESGA)

PhD Inter-University Program in Equity and Innovation in Education

University: University of Santiago de Compostela, University of Oviedo, University of Cantabria, University of A Coruña and University of Vigo

Status: In progress

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- [Untelligente Technologien für innovation in der lehrerausbildung. das](#)

ekt-handbuch (Deutsch)

3.4 Multimedia material

- Promotional videos. (Coming soon)
- Youtube Canal

3.5 Newsletters

> O28-WP8 EKT newsletters

- Newsletter 1
- Newsletter 2
- Newsletter 3

3.6 Brochure

> O21-WP8 Project poster

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- Poster 2

Brochure:

- English
- Español

- Deutsch
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- Français

3.7 EACEA Erasmus+ Knowledge Alliances Dissemination Sheet

EACEA Erasmus+ Knowledge Alliances Dissemination Sheet

3.8 Media news

(Coming soon)

3.9 Final conference

> O4-WP1 Final International Conference

The final conference of the **EKT Project** **Smart Technologies for Innovation in Teacher Training** was held on 13 April 2023 in the auditorium of the Faculty of Education of the University of Santiago de Compostela and streamed online.

The conference generated a lot of attention. 352 students, teachers, school principals, researchers, teacher trainers, educators and managers of ITE institutions and e-learning practitioners from 52 nationalities registered for event. In the end 112 persons participated in person, while 235 people attended online.

EDUCATIONAL KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

Co-funded by the Erasmus+ Programme of the European Union

EKT Project Final Conference
Smart Technologies for Innovation
in Teacher Training

13, APRIL 23 | 11 A.M. CET

Faculty of Education Sciences, Campus Vida
 University of Santiago de Compostela

Coordinator: USC (UNIVERSIDADE DE SANTIAGO DE COMPOSTELA) www.ektproject.eu

Partners: CESCA, die Berater, MARNO, FH Wien, lusoinfo multimedia, editora, BeezNest

Streaming: Registration: <https://ektproject.eu/conference/>

3.10 National events

> O26-WP8 EKT national events

SPANISH NATIONAL EVENT 1:

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SPANISH NATIONAL EVENT 4:

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(<http://www.conferenciadecanososeducacion.es/>)

3.11 O27-WP8 Report on exploitation and dissemination plan

(Coming soon)

Co-funded by the
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of the European Union

The EKT project has been funded with support from the European Commission. The European Commission's support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

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> O8-WP4 Advanced e-learning system

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- Fernández-Morante, C., Casal-Otero, L., Cebreiro, B., Mareque León, F., Rodríguez Malmierca, M.J. & Felpeto Guerrero, A. (2023). EKT methodology: an open and collaborative strategy to facilitate school placements for future teachers. In . Elizabeth Langran (Ed.), *Proceedings of Society for Information Technology & Teacher Education International Conference* (pp. 1534-1536). New Orleans, LA, United States: Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (ACE). Retrieved April 3, 2023 from <https://www.learntechlib.org/primary/p/222028/>.
- Felpeto-Guerrero, A., Rodríguez-Malmierca, M.J., Fernández-Morante, C. & Cebreiro-López, B. (2023). Pilot evaluation of the EKT trans-national elearning platform to support in school placement. In Elizabeth Langran (Ed.), *Proceedings of Society for Information Technology & Teacher Education International Conference* (pp. 973-978). New Orleans, LA, United States: Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (ACE). Retrieved April 3, 2023 from <https://www.learntechlib.org/primary/p/221954/>.

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Directors: M. Carmen Fernández Morante (USC) and Beatriz Cebreiro López (USC).

PhD program in Education

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Status: In progress

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ekt-handbuch (Deutsch)

3.4 Multimedia material

- Promotional videos. (Coming soon)
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3.5 Newsletters

> O28-WP8 EKT newsletters

- Newsletter 1
- Newsletter 2
- Newsletter 3

3.6 Brochure

> O21-WP8 Project poster

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- Español

- Deutsch
- Português
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3.7 EACEA Erasmus+ Knowledge Alliances Dissemination Sheet

EACEA Erasmus+ Knowledge Alliances Dissemination Sheet

3.8 Media news

(Coming soon)

3.9 Final conference

> O4-WP1 Final International Conference

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Partners: CESCA, die Berater, MARNO, FH Wien, lusoinfo multimedia, editora, BeezNest

Streaming: Registration: <https://ektproject.eu/conference/>

3.10 National events

> O26-WP8 EKT national events

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(<http://www.conferenciadecanososeducacion.es/>)

3.11 O27-WP8 Report on exploitation and dissemination plan

(Coming soon)

Co-funded by the
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The EKT project has been funded with support from the European Commission. The European Commission's support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

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1. Mentors and student teachers materials

> O6-WP3 Educational and technological framework

> O8-WP4 Advanced e-learning system

(Select the preferred language in the browser. To test EKT advanced e-learning system, use the credentials available in O8-WP4 report)

- English
- Spanish
- Deutsch
- Portuguese

> O9-WP4 Mobile app development

[Download Android version](#)

(To test EKT advanced e-learning system, use the credentials

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> **O10-WP5 Training platform for SPOC**

> **O11-WP5 Training contents PHW**

Visualization links

- English
- Spanish
- German
- Portuguese

Scorm download

- English
- Spanish
- German
- Portuguese

> **O13-WP6 Pilot guide**

- English
- German
- Portuguese
- Spanish

2. Reports

> **O5-WP2 Report on in-school placements needs and possibilities of the technologies**

> **O7-WP4 Technical analysis report**

> **O14-WP6 Pilot report**

> **O17-WP7 Evaluation of users satisfaction**

> **O18-WP7 Evaluation on impact of EKT proposal**

3. Dissemination materials

3.1 Scientific publications, Conference papers & Theses

> **(O23-WP8) Press release scientific articles**

- Fernández-Morante, C., Cebreiro-López, B., Rodríguez-Malmierca, M.-J., & Casal-Otero, L. (2021). Adaptive Learning Supported by Learning Analytics for Student Teachers' Personalized Training during in-School Practices. *Sustainability*, 14(1), 124. MDPI AG. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su14010124>
- Brandão Carvalho, J.A. & Fernández-Morante, C., et al. (2023). Report on in-school placements needs and possibilities of the technologies (EKT Output 5). Universidade do Minho. Instituto de

Educação. Centro de Investigação em Educação. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7806236>

- Fernández-Morante, M.C., Bienzle, H., & et al. (2023). *Smart Technologies for Innovation in Teacher Training. The EKT Handbook*. Zenodo. Die Berater Unternehmensberatungs GmbH. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7818021>
- Leránoz-Iglesias, M. M., Fernández-Morante, C., Cebreiro-López, B., & Abeal-Pereira, C. (2023). Study on the Collaboration between University and Educational Centers Mentors in the Development of the In-School Education Placements in Official University Degrees Qualifying for the Teaching Profession: The Case of the University of Santiago de Compostela. *Education Sciences*, 13(2), 104. MDPI AG. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/educsci13020104>
- Casal-Otero, L., Catala, A., Fernández-Morante, C. et al. AI literacy in K-12: a systematic literature review. *IJ STEM Ed* 10, 29 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-023-00418-7>

> (O24-WP8) Presentations in conferences and events at european and wider level

- Egan, A., Revyakina, E., Georgeson, J., Cebreiro López, B., Fernández Morante, C., Latorre Ruiz, E. & Strasser, T. (2021). EKT, a trans-national platform to support school placement. In E. Langran & L. Archambault (Eds.), *Proceedings of Society for Information Technology & Teacher Education International Conference* (pp. 656-661). Online, United States: Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE). Retrieved April 3, 2023 from <https://www.learntechlib.org/primary/p/219196/>.

- Fernández-Morante, C., Cebreiro, B., Casal-Otero, L., Leránoz-Iglesias, M., Rodríguez-Malmierca, M. J., & Felpeto-Guerrero, A. (noviembre,2022). EKT Una plataforma integral para el soporte de futuros/as docentes. (p.378–380) [Comunicación]. XXV Congreso Internacional EDUTEC 2022, Palma, España.
<https://edutec2022.uib.es/libro-de-actas/>
- Fernández-Morante, C., Cebreiro, B., Latorre Ruiz, E., e Casal, L., (2022). Las tecnologías emergentes como herramienta de apoyo en el Prácticum de la formación inicial del profesorado. International congress education and knowledge. ICON ISBN: 978-84-19312-37-2
- Egan, A., Georgeson, J., Revyakina, E., Strasser, T., Cebreiro, B., Fernandez-Morante, C. e Latorre-Ruiz, E. (2022). EKT, a pilot project exploring the use and impact of a smart technological system to support school placement in five European countries. In E. Langran (Ed.), *Proceedings of Society for Information Technology & Teacher Education International Conference* (pp. 2167-2172). San Diego, CA, United States: Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE). Retrieved May 3, 2022 from <https://www.learntechlib.org/primary/p/221048/>
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